

Supplementary table S2: Scientific identifications provided by researchers for the plants documented in their studies. Legend: * = plant cited in different studies in which at least one record lacked identification or presented divergent identifications (in the latter case, divergent identifications are separated by semicolons); N.I. = Not identified.

Ethnospecies	No. of Citations	Scientific Name	Family	Reported Uses
Avocado	2	<i>Persea americana</i> Mill.	Lauraceae	Skin hydration; wound healing
Abre-caminho	1	<i>Justicia pectoralis</i> Jacq.	Acanthaceae	Skin care
Açaí*	6	<i>Euterpe precatoria</i> Mart.; <i>Euterpe oleracea</i> Mart.	Arecaceae	Soap; skin care; hair care; apply to hair; cosmetics; wound healing
Rosemary* and lavender	2	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i> L.	Lamiaceae	Hair loss; hair washing
Lavender	1	<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i> Mill.	Lamiaceae	Wound healing
Algodão roxo*	2	<i>Gossypium barbadense</i> L.; <i>Gossypium hirsutum</i> L.	Malvaceae	Wound healing
Plum	1	<i>Prunus</i> sp.	Rosaceae	Wound healing
Blackberry	1	<i>Morus nigra</i> L.	Moraceae	Hair loss
Amor-crescido*	5	<i>Portulaca</i> subsect. <i>Pilosae</i> D. Legrand; <i>Portulaca pilosa</i> L.	Portulacaceae	Hair washing; hair loss
Andiroba*	9	<i>Carapa guianensis</i> Aubl.	Meliaceae	Wound healing; hair hydration; cosmetics; lice treatment; massage
African andiroba	1	<i>Carapa procera</i> D.C.	N.I.	Cosmetics
Andiroba-de-rama	1	<i>Fevillea</i> sp.	Cucurbitaceae	Soap
Arnica	1	<i>Arnica acaulis</i> (Walter) Britton, Sterns &	Asteraceae	Wound healing

Poggenb.				
Rue	3	<i>Ruta graveolens</i> L.	Rutaceae	Lice treatment; wound healing
Babaçu*	4	<i>Attalea speciosa</i> Mart.; <i>Attalea eichleri</i> (Drude) A. J. Hend.; <i>Orbignya speciosa</i> Martius; <i>Orbignya phalerata</i> Martius; <i>Attalea</i> <i>glassmanii</i> Zona	N.I.	Apply to hair; cosmetics; exfoliation
Aloe vera*	37	<i>Aloe vera</i> (L.) Burm.f.	Xanthorrhoeaceae; Asphodelaceae; Asparagaceae; Liliaceae	Hair care; hair loss; hair strengthening; burns; hair hydration; wound healing; skin care; skin blemishes; cosmetics
Bacaba	2	<i>Oenocarpus mapora</i> H.Karst.	Arecaceae	Skin care; hair care
Balsam tree	1	<i>Myroxylon balsamum</i> (L.) Harms	Fabaceae	Wound healing
Barbatimão	1	<i>Stryphnodendron adstringens</i> (Mart.) Coville	Fabaceae	Wound healing
Burdock	1	<i>Arctium lappa</i> L.	Asteraceae	Wound healing
Breu	1	<i>Protium heptaphyllum</i> (Aubl.) Marchand	N.I.	Hair removal
Cocoa	1	<i>Theobroma cacao</i> L.	Malvaceae	Wound healing
Cajarana	1	<i>Jacaranda copaia</i> (Aubl.) D.Don	Bignoniaceae	Wound healing
Cashew	4	<i>Anacardium occidentale</i> L.	Anacardiaceae	Skin care; wound healing
Cajucara	1	<i>Croton cajucara</i> Benth.	Euphorbiaceae	Wound healing
Calêndula	1	<i>Calendula arvensis</i> L.	Asteraceae	Wound healing
Chamomile*	3	<i>Chamomilla recutita</i> (L.) Rauschert; <i>Matricaria</i> <i>chamomilla</i> L.	Asteraceae	Wound healing; cosmetics
Wild chamomile	1	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> L.	Asteraceae	Wound healing
Lemongrass	1	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i> (DC.) Stapf	N.I.	Hair loss
Holy grass	3	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i> (DC.) Stapf	Poaceae	Cosmetics; hair loss

Carnaubinha	1	<i>Copernicia prunifera</i> (Mill.) H.E.Moore	N.I.	Cosmetics
Carvão Branco	1	<i>Callisthene fasciculata</i> Mart.	N.I.	Skin blemishes
Catuaba	1	<i>Abuta</i> sp.	Menispermaceae	Wound healing
Chapéu-de-couro	1	<i>Echinodorus macrophyllus</i> (Kunth) Micheli	Alismataceae	Wound healing
Cipó-de-mosseguim	1	<i>Parabignonia steyermarkii</i> Sandwith	Bignoniaceae	Wound
Cipó-de-mucunã	1	<i>Dioclea</i> sp.	Fabaceae	Hair loss
Cocão	2	<i>Attalea tessmannii</i> Burret	Arecaceae	Skin care; hair care
Confrei	2	<i>Symphytum officinale</i> L.	Boraginaceae	Wound healing
Copaiba*	6	<i>Copaifera</i> spp.; <i>Copaifera langsdorffii</i> Desf.; <i>Copaifera multijuga</i> Hayne	Fabaceae; Caesalpiniaceae	Wound healing
Clove	1	<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> (L.) Merr. & L.M.Perry	Myrtaceae	Wound healing
Lemon balm	1	<i>Lippia alba</i> (Mill.) N.E.Br. ex Britton & P.Wilson	Lamiaceae	Cosmetics
Erva-de-passar	2	<i>Alternanthera dentata</i> (Moench) Stuchlík ex R.E.Fr.	Amaranthaceae	Skin care; wound healing
Erva-de-Santa-Maria	1	<i>Chenopodium ambrosioides</i> L.	Chenopodiaceae	Hair loss
Espada-de-São-Jorge	1	<i>Sansevieria zeylanica</i> (L.) Willd.	Asparagaceae	Cosmetics
Espinheira-santa	1	<i>Maytenus ilicifolia</i> Mart. ex Reissek	N.I.	Wound healing
Ginger	2	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Roscoe	Zingiberaceae	Cosmetics
Guava	4	<i>Psidium guajava</i> L.; <i>Psidium pyrifera</i> L.	Myrtaceae	Hair loss; wound healing
Guaraná	1	<i>Paullinia cupana</i> Kunth	Sapindaceae	Skin care
Hibiscus	1	<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i> L.	Malvaceae	Hair loss
Mint	2	<i>Mentha piperita</i> L.	Lamiaceae	Cosmetics; treatment
Ibisco	1	<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i> L.	Fabaceae	Hair strengthening
Imbé	1	N.I.	N.I.	Wound healing
Jambu	2	<i>Acmella oleracea</i> (L.) R.K.Jansen	Asteraceae	Wound healing

Java plum	1	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	Myrtaceae	Wound healing
Jarina	1	<i>Phytelephas macrocarpa</i> Ruiz & Pav.	Arecaceae	Wound healing
Jatobá*	1	<i>Hymenaea parvifolia</i> Huber; <i>Hymenaea courbaril</i> L.	Caesalpinaceae; Fabaceae	Soap; hair loss
Jucá*	3	<i>Caesalpinia ferrea</i> Mart. ex Tul.	Fabaceae	Dandruff; wound healing
Orange	2	<i>Citrus sinensis</i> (L.) Osbeck or <i>Citrus aurantium</i> L.	Rutaceae	Cosmetics
Língua de sogra	1	<i>Sansevieria trifasciata</i> Prain	Asparagaceae	Skin care
Malvarisco	1	<i>Piper umbellatum</i> L.	Piperaceae	Wound healing
Mango	1	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Anacardiaceae	Wound healing
Mangava-brava	1	<i>Lafoensia pacari</i> A.St.-Hil.	N.I.	Wound healing
Passion fruit	1	<i>Passiflora edulis</i> Sims	Passifloraceae	Hair loss
Marupá	1	N.I.	N.I.	Itching; wound
Mastruz*	4	<i>Chenopodium ambrosioides</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	Wound healing
Melaleuca	1	<i>Melaleuca alternifolia</i> (Maiden & Betche) Cheel	Myrtaceae	Wound healing
Melão de São Caetano	2	<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	Cucurbitaceae	Itching; skin mycosis
Meracilina	1	N.I.	N.I.	Wound healing
Mulateiro	1	<i>Calycophyllum spruceanum</i> (Benth.) Hook.f. ex K.Schum.	Rubiaceae	Skin blemishes
Murmurú	1	<i>Astrocaryum murumuru</i> Mart.	N.I.	Cosmetics
Orelha-de-onça	1	<i>Geogenanthus poeppigii</i> (Miq.) Faden	Commelinaceae	Wound healing
Ouricuri	1	<i>Attalea phalerata</i> Mart. ex Spreng.	N.I.	Cosmetics
Patauí*	7	<i>Oenocarpus bataua</i> Mart.	Arecaceae	Soap; skin care; hair care; wound healing; apply to hair
Patchouli	2	N.I.	N.I.	Hair loss
Pau-da-Angola	1	<i>Piper divaricatum</i> G. Mey.	Piperaceae	Hair loss

Pião branco	1	<i>Jatropha mollissima</i> (Pohl) Baill.	Euphorbiaceae	Wound healing
Pião roxo	2	<i>Jatropha gossypifolia</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Wound healing
Picão	1	<i>Bidens pilosa</i> L.	Asteraceae	Wound healing
Pinhão Roxo	1	<i>Jatropha gossypifolia</i> L.	N.I.	Wound healing
Pirarucu	1	<i>Kalanchoe pinnata</i> (Lam.) Pers.	Arapaimidae	Burns
Pracaxi	1	N.I.	N.I.	Cosmetics
Quina	1	<i>Geissospermum</i> sp.	Apocynaceae	Lice treatment
Salsa	2	<i>Smilax</i> sp.	Smilacaceae	Skin blemishes; itching
Fern	1	N.I.	N.I.	Hair loss
Sangra-d'água	1	<i>Croton urucurana</i> Baill.	N.I.	Wound healing
Sangue de Dragão	1	<i>Croton floribundus</i> Spreng.	Euphorbiaceae	Wound healing
Tangerine	1	<i>Citrus reticulata</i> Blanco	Rutaceae	Hair loss
Terramycin	1	N.I.	N.I.	Wound healing
Trapueraba	1	N.I.	N.I.	Itching
Tucum	2	<i>Bactris setosa</i> Mart.	N.I.	Hair care; wound healing
Tucumã	2	<i>Astrocaryum aculeatum</i> G.Mey.	Areaceae	Soap; cosmetics
Uxi	1	<i>Endopleura uchi</i> (Huber) Cuatrec.	Humiriaceae	Wound healing

Source: Authors